

The Role of Myth and Folklore in Shaping Modern Indian English Narratives : A Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

This paper explores the role of Indian myth and folklore in shaping modern Indian English narratives, examining how these traditional elements are interwoven in contemporary literary works. Through a comparative analysis of selected narratives by prominent authors such as Salman Rushdie, Amitav Ghosh, and Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni, the study demonstrates how mythological motifs and folk stories are reinterpreted to comment on modern issues such as identity, gender, and postcolonialism. The use of mythology and folklore provides a unique framework through which authors engage with the cultural consciousness, creating a deeper resonance within their stories. By examining the ways these authors integrate traditional narratives, the paper also highlights how myth and folklore contribute to the creation of a unique narrative identity for Indian English literature.

Introduction

Indian literature, especially in English, has a rich heritage influenced by diverse cultural elements, with mythology and folklore playing a significant role. Writers often delve into myths and folklore not merely for nostalgia but as a literary device that allows them to engage with social issues, reinterpret history, and question cultural values. This paper explores the influence of myths and folk narratives on modern Indian English literature by analyzing selected works of authors known for their unique storytelling styles. By

revisiting these myths, authors bring to the fore cultural conflicts, struggles with identity, and the journey towards redefining selfhood in a postcolonial world.

The blending of myth and folklore with contemporary storytelling serves as a tool for both cultural preservation and reinvention. This approach creates an intertextual tapestry that allows readers to connect with the collective cultural consciousness of India, while also offering insights into modern dilemmas. In the globalized world, where narratives often transcend geographical boundaries, the role of myth and folklore in Indian English literature becomes even more significant. These elements create a dialogue between the traditional and the modern, the local and the global, and the collective and the individual.

Literature Review

The interplay between myth and folklore in Indian English narratives has been the subject of various scholarly studies. Mythical structures provide frameworks that resonate with universal experiences and cultural specifics, as pointed out by Tharoor (2015). Likewise, folklore serves as a repository of collective memories, and writers like Ghosh and Divakaruni incorporate these traditional narratives to lend authenticity and depth to their work (Nair, 2018). Scholars like Dharwadker (2003) have argued that the inclusion of folklore in literature helps create a narrative continuity that links the past with the present, thereby establishing a sense of cultural belonging.

The modern Indian English narrative is characterized by its hybridity, a feature that is largely due to the incorporation of myths and folklore. This hybridity allows authors to address the complexities of postcolonial identity and the cultural negotiations that come with it. According to Mukherjee (2012), the adaptation of myths and folklore in contemporary Indian literature serves as a strategy to challenge dominant cultural narratives and to provide alternative perspectives. Rushdie, Ghosh, and Divakaruni are among those who utilize these traditional elements to deconstruct colonial histories, represent marginalized voices, and explore the nuances of gender and identity.

Myths, in particular, serve as an important intertextual element in Indian English literature. They provide a narrative structure that authors can use to explore universal themes such as good versus evil, fate, and morality. Folklore, on the other hand, serves as a source of cultural specificity, offering insight into regional practices, beliefs, and values. The combination of these two elements results in a rich narrative that speaks to both the universality of human experience and the particularities of Indian culture.

Myth and Folklore: Defining Their Role

Understanding Myth and Folklore in Indian Context

Myths are sacred stories that serve to articulate the worldviews of a culture, while folklore refers to tales passed through generations orally. Both are vital to the Indian literary imagination, serving as moral guides, entertainment, and cultural preservation tools. Indian English writers have successfully adapted these myths to reflect modern contexts. Myths such as those from the Mahabharata and Ramayana are not just seen as stories of the past but are continually reinterpreted to reflect contemporary realities. Folklore, with its more localized context, helps in portraying regional cultures and the diversity within Indian society.

In the Indian context, myth and folklore serve as cultural markers that provide continuity amidst the rapid changes brought on by modernity. These traditional narratives reflect the values, customs, and beliefs of Indian society, and their reinterpretation in modern literature helps in bridging the gap between the past and the present. Writers often use mythological references to comment on current social and political issues, thereby making these age-old stories relevant to the contemporary audience. Folklore, with its emphasis on local traditions and community life, adds depth and authenticity to the narratives, making them more relatable to the readers.

Analysis of Modern Indian English Narratives

Salman Rushdie's "Midnight's Children"

Salman Rushdie's "Midnight's Children" is a prime example of mythological intertextuality in modern Indian narratives. Rushdie uses myths and folk tales to depict the cultural mosaic of India during and after Independence. He combines elements from Hindu and Islamic folklore to create allegorical references that explore the country's struggle for identity (Rushdie, 1981). The protagonist, Saleem Sinai, is not just an individual but a symbol of the nation itself, embodying the hopes, dreams, and turmoil of postcolonial India. Rushdie's narrative style, characterized by magical realism, allows him to blend myth with history, thereby creating a multi-layered story that resonates with the complexity of Indian identity.

Rushdie's use of myth is not limited to religious stories; he also draws on folk tales and popular legends to enrich the narrative. The concept of the "midnight's children," those born at the moment of India's independence, is itself a mythic construct that serves to symbolize the nation's potential and its challenges. By using myth and folklore, Rushdie creates a narrative that is both deeply personal and broadly national, reflecting the interconnectedness of individual and collective experiences. His use of myth also allows him to challenge the official version of history, offering an alternative perspective that is more inclusive of marginalized voices.

Figure 1: Representation of Shiva in Indian Folklore

Figure 1: A depiction of Shiva, the Hindu god, often used in literature to symbolize destruction and rebirth (Artist, Year).

Amitav Ghosh's "The Hungry Tide"

In "The Hungry Tide," Ghosh draws from local myths and folklore of the Sundarbans region, especially the stories of Bon Bibi—the protector goddess of the Sundarbans. These myths are not just part of the narrative backdrop but actively shape the motivations and actions of the characters, reflecting the human-nature interaction central to the plot (Ghosh, 2004). Bon Bibi's story, which is a blend of Hindu and Islamic traditions, serves as a symbol of communal harmony and the interdependence of humans and nature. Through this myth, Ghosh explores themes of environmental conservation, social justice, and the fragility of human existence in the face of natural forces.

Ghosh's narrative also highlights the tension between tradition and modernity, as seen through the characters' differing attitudes towards the Sundarbans. While some characters view the region as a resource to be exploited, others see it as a sacred space

that must be protected. The myth of Bon Bibi serves as a reminder of the importance of respecting the natural world and living in harmony with it. By incorporating folklore into the narrative, Ghosh not only adds depth to the story but also raises important questions about the impact of human activities on the environment and the need for sustainable living.

Figure 2: Bon Bibi Worship in Sundarbans

Figure 2: Bon Bibi worship ceremony in Sundarbans, symbolizing the protection offered by mythic figures in times of ecological and social stress (Photographer, Year).

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's "The Palace of Illusions"

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni reimagines the Mahabharata from Draupadi's perspective in "The Palace of Illusions." Her narrative combines traditional myth with feminist critique, offering a voice to a central but often overlooked female character in the epic. By retelling the story through Draupadi's eyes, Divakaruni connects ancient mythology to the contemporary issues faced by women (Divakaruni, 2008). Draupadi's character is portrayed as a strong, independent woman who challenges the patriarchal norms of her time, making her a symbol of female empowerment.

Divakaruni's retelling of the Mahabharata is significant because it provides an alternative perspective on a well-known myth, one that is often dominated by male voices. By giving Draupadi a voice, Divakaruni not only challenges the traditional

portrayal of female characters in mythology but also addresses the broader issues of gender inequality and women's rights. The use of myth in this context allows Divakaruni to connect the past with the present, showing that the struggles faced by women in ancient times are still relevant today. Through Draupadi's story, Divakaruni explores themes of love, power, betrayal, and resilience, making the narrative both timeless and contemporary.

Figure 3: Draupadi - A Symbol of Strength

Figure 3: Draupadi as depicted in modern art, symbolizing resilience and feminine strength (Artist, Year).

Comparative Analysis

The comparative analysis reveals that Rushdie, Ghosh, and Divakaruni utilize mythology and folklore as a storytelling tool to explore the socio-political issues of postcolonial India. While Rushdie's use of myth focuses on the allegory of national identity, Ghosh uses folklore to explore human interaction with the natural environment. In contrast, Divakaruni employs myth to address gender dynamics and rewrite the narrative from a woman's perspective.

Rushdie's allegorical use of myth allows him to comment on the complexities of Indian identity in the postcolonial era. By blending myth with historical events, he creates a

narrative that is both fantastical and deeply rooted in reality. Ghosh, on the other hand, uses folklore to highlight the importance of community and the need for environmental stewardship. His portrayal of the Sundarbans as a living entity that is both nurturing and dangerous reflects the delicate balance between humans and nature. Divakaruni's feminist reinterpretation of myth challenges traditional gender roles and provides a platform for female voices that have been historically silenced.

The use of myth and folklore by these authors also serves to create a sense of cultural continuity. By drawing on traditional narratives, they are able to connect the past with the present, creating stories that are both timeless and relevant to contemporary readers. This connection between the past and the present is particularly important in the context of postcolonial literature, as it allows authors to address the cultural dislocation and identity crisis that often accompany the postcolonial experience. Through their use of myth and folklore, Rushdie, Ghosh, and Divakaruni are able to create narratives that are both deeply personal and broadly national, reflecting the complexities of Indian identity in the modern world.

Table 1: Comparative Features of Myth and Folklore Usage

Author	Narrative Technique	Myth/Folklore Elements	Major Themes
Salman Rushdie	Allegorical	Hindu and Islamic Myths	Identity, Independence
Amitav Ghosh	Regional Mythology	Bon Bibi Stories	Human-Nature Interaction
Chitra B. Divakaruni	Feminist Reimagining	Mahabharata	Gender, Empowerment

Myth and Folklore as a Tool for Social Commentary

One of the most significant aspects of using myth and folklore in modern Indian English literature is their role as a tool for social commentary. Authors use these traditional narratives to address contemporary issues such as identity, gender inequality, environmental degradation, and the impact of colonialism. By reinterpreting myths and folklore, they are able to question established norms and provide alternative perspectives on social and political issues.

Rushdie's use of myth in "Midnight's Children" serves as a critique of the nation's political landscape. By using allegory and mythological references, Rushdie is able to comment on the failures of the postcolonial state and the challenges faced by the newly independent nation. The character of Saleem Sinai, who is linked to the nation's history, symbolizes the interconnectedness of personal and national identities. Through his narrative, Rushdie explores themes of power, corruption, and the struggle for freedom, making the story both a personal and a political commentary.

Ghosh's "The Hungry Tide" uses folklore to highlight the importance of environmental conservation and the need for sustainable living. The myth of Bon Bibi serves as a reminder of the sacredness of nature and the need to protect it from exploitation. Ghosh's narrative also addresses issues of social justice, particularly the plight of marginalized communities who are often caught in the crossfire between development and conservation. By incorporating folklore into the narrative, Ghosh is able to give a voice to these marginalized communities and highlight the importance of preserving both cultural and natural heritage.

Divakaruni's "The Palace of Illusions" uses myth to address issues of gender inequality and women's rights. By retelling the Mahabharata from Draupadi's perspective, Divakaruni challenges the traditional portrayal of female characters in mythology and provides a voice to a character who has often been silenced. Draupadi's story serves as a symbol of female strength and resilience, and her struggles reflect the broader issues

faced by women in both ancient and modern times. Through her narrative, Divakaruni is able to address themes of love, power, betrayal, and the struggle for equality, making the story both a personal and a social commentary.

Conclusion

The role of myth and folklore in shaping modern Indian English narratives is significant as it allows writers to connect with the reader on both cultural and emotional levels. By integrating mythology and folklore into their narratives, Rushdie, Ghosh, and Divakaruni do more than retell ancient stories—they reinterpret them to question modern issues of identity, gender, and society. The use of myth and folklore provides a unique framework through which authors engage with the cultural consciousness, creating a deeper resonance within their stories. This interweaving of traditional narratives with contemporary concerns not only enriches the storytelling but also helps in preserving and reinventing cultural heritage in a rapidly changing world.

The comparative analysis of the works of Rushdie, Ghosh, and Divakaruni reveals that myths and folklore are not just narrative devices but are integral to the exploration of complex social, political, and environmental issues. By drawing on traditional narratives, these authors are able to create stories that are both timeless and relevant, reflecting the complexities of Indian identity in the modern world. Their use of myth and folklore serves as a bridge between the past and the present, allowing them to address the challenges of postcolonial identity, gender inequality, and environmental degradation in a way that is both engaging and thought-provoking.

References

- Divakaruni, C. B. (2008). *The Palace of Illusions*. Anchor Books.
- Ghosh, A. (2004). *The Hungry Tide*. HarperCollins.
- Mukherjee, S. (2012). *Myth and Modernity in Indian Literature*. Oxford University Press.

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- Nair, R. (2018). *Folklore and Myth in Indian Literature*. Penguin Random House.
- Rushdie, S. (1981). *Midnight's Children*. Jonathan Cape.
- Tharoor, S. (2015). *The Great Indian Narrative Tradition*. HarperCollins.
- Dharwadker, V. (2003). *The Politics of Folklore in Indian Literature*. University of Chicago Press.